

Flavonoids of *Echinops echinatus*

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Abstract : Six flavonoids, 7-hydroxyisoflavone, kaempferol-4'-methylether, kaempferol-7-methylether, kaempferol, kaempferol-3-O- α -L-rhamnoside and myrecetin-3-O- α -L-rhamnoside has been isolated from the whole plant of *Echinops echinatus*.

Keywords : Medicinal plants, flavonoids.

Echinops echinatus Roxb. (Compositae) is distributed throughout India and used in Indian medicine for the treatment of chronic fever, inflammations and various other diseases¹. A number of terpenoids, flavonoids and other constituents have earlier been reported² from this plant. Here we report the isolation of further six flavonoids.

The whole plant (3.5 kg) was collected locally and dried material was extracted with MeOH in a soxhlet extractor. The methanolic extract (75 g) was chromatographed over SiO₂ gel column. The eluants collected from benzene-ethylacetate (8 : 1), (4 : 1), (3 : 1), (1 : 2), ethylacetate, ethylacetate-methanol (9 : 1) and (4 : 1) on crystallisation from MeOH furnished respectively 7-hydroxyisoflavone³ (15 mg), m.p. 215 °C, kaempferol-4'-methylether⁴ (21 mg), m.p. 223–225 °C; kaempferol-7-methylether⁴ (25 mg), m.p. 218–220 °C, kaempferol⁴ (32 mg), m.p. 273–275 °C, kaempferol-3-O- α -L-rhamnoside⁵ (28 mg), m.p. 177–179 °C and myrecetin-3-O- α -L-rhamnoside⁵ (24 mg), m.p. 211–213 °C.

7-Hydroxyisoflavone : It exhibited UV $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 260 (log ϵ 4.13), 290 sh (3.40), 315 sh (3.34) nm; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200–3600 (OH), 1655 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 300 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.90 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-8), 6.94 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-5), 7.39 (m, H-3', H-4', H-5'), 7.56 (m, H-2', H-6'), 7.92 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-6), 8.36 (s, H-2), 10.80 (br s, OH); 100 MHz ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 153.4 (C-2), 123.3 (C-3), 174.0 (C-4), 116.4 (C-4a), 127.0 (C-5), 115.0 (C-6), 162.4 (C-7), 101.9 (C-8), 157.1 (C-8a), 131.8 (C-1'), 127.8 (C-2'), 128.6 (C-3'), 127.4 (C-4'), 128.6 (C-5'), 127.8 (C-6'); HRMS; *m/z* 238.0629

(M⁺, C₁₅H₁₀O₃); 210, 137.0238 (C₇H₅O₃), 102.0469 (C₈H₆).

Kaempferol-4'-methylether : It exhibited UV $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 250 sh (log ϵ 4.17), 270 (4.20), 300 (3.70), 320 (3.92), 368 (4.30) nm; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200–3600 (br, OH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.84 (s, Ar-OCH₃), 6.33 (d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.72 (d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 6.94 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 8.09 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.51 (s, OH), 10.15 (s, OH), 12.45 (s, OH); MS, *m/z* 300 (M⁺, C₁₆H₁₂O₆), 272, 257, 229, 154, 148, 124; with CH₂N₂ it gave trimethylether derivative, m.p. 151–153 °C, C₁₉ H₁₈O₆ (M⁺, 342).

Kaempferol-7-methylether : It exhibited UV $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 254 (log ϵ 4.25), 266 (4.20), 323 (4.10), 365 (4.40) nm; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3150–3550 (br, OH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 3.70 (s, Ar-OCH₃), 6.11 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-6), 6.46 (d, *J* 2 Hz, H-8), 6.67 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 7.74 (d, *J* 8 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.11 (s, OH), 9.71 (s, OH), 11.98 (s, OH); MS, *m/z* 300 (M⁺, C₁₆H₁₂O₆), 272, 257, 229, 166, 138, 134; with acetic anhydride and pyridine, it gave triacetate, m.p. 201–203 °C, C₂₂H₁₈O₉ (M⁺, 426).

Kaempferol : It exhibited UV $\lambda_{\max}$ (MeOH) 252 sh (log ϵ 4.20), 266 (4.25), 292 (3.95), 322 sh (4.10), 366 (4.38) nm; IR $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3320 (OH), 1660 cm⁻¹ (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆) δ 6.22 (d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-6), 6.46 (d, *J* 2.2 Hz, H-8), 6.68 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 8.11 (d, *J* 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 9.44 (s, OH), 10.22 (s, OH), 12.56 (s, OH); MS, *m/z* 286 (M⁺,

$C_{15}H_{10}O_6$), 258, 152, 134, 124.

Kaempferol-3-O- α -L-rhamnoside : It exhibited UV λ_{max} (MeOH) 264 sh (log ϵ 4.12), 313 sh (3.82), 343 (4.00) nm; IR ν_{max} (KBr) 3200–3600 (br, OH), 1660 cm^{-1} (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 6.10 (d, J 2 Hz, H-6), 6.28 (d, J 2 Hz, H-8), 6.93 (d, J 9 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 7.75 (d, J 9 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 12.66 (br s, 3 $\times$ OH) and eleven rhamnosyl protons [δ 0.81 (d, J 5 Hz, CH_3), 3.13 (2H, m), 3.46 (1H, m), 4.00 (1H, br s), 4.88 (3H, br s, OH), 5.32 (d, J 2 Hz, anomeric H)]; elemental analysis (Found : C, 57.90; H, 4.54. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{10}$: C, 58.30; H, 4.60%); acid hydrolysis gave kaempferol (m.m.p., co-TLC).

Myrecetin-3-O- α -L-rhamnoside : It exhibited UV λ_{max} (MeOH) 258 (log ϵ 4.20), 305 sh (3.12), 353 (4.00) nm; IR ν_{max} (KBr) 3200–3600 (br, OH), 1660 cm^{-1} (chelated carbonyl); 90 MHz 1H NMR (DMSO- d_6) δ 6.21 (d, J 2 Hz, H-6), 6.38 (d, J 2 Hz, H-8), 6.92 (br s, H-2', H-6'), 12.75 (br s, 6 $\times$ OH) and eleven rhamnosyl protons [δ 0.86 (d, J 6 Hz, CH_3), 3.36 (2H, m), 3.59 (1H, m), 4.02 (1H, br s), 5.40 (3H, br s), 5.23 (d, J 2 Hz, anomeric-

H)]; elemental analysis (Found : C, 54.30; H, 4.28. Calcd. for $C_{21}H_{20}O_{12}$: C, 54.30; H, 4.32 %); acid hydrolysis gave myrecetin (m.m.p., co-TLC, 1H NMR, MS and superimposable IR).

The structures of all the above compounds were supported by a study of UV with shift reagents and direct comparison with authentic samples (m.m.p., co-TLC and superimposable IR).

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